

FRANCE

FRANCE

SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL BASIS OF FORMING MUSIC PERCEPTION IN SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF STUDYING THE WORKS OF ROMANTIC COMPOSERS

Rustamjonova Dilhavas Ravshanbek qizi

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami
1st year master's student in the specialty "Music Education and Art"

Trigulova A.Kh.

Scientific supervisor:

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15005967>

Abstract: This study is devoted to the study of the scientific and theoretical foundations of the formation of music perception among high school students in the process of studying the works of romantic composers.

Key words: Romantic composers, music perception, high school students, music education, scientific-theoretical foundations, aesthetic taste, psychological approach, pedagogical methodology, musical thinking.

Introduction.

Music is one of the strongest forms of art that directly affects the human psyche and emotions. In particular, the music of the Romantic period is distinguished by its high artistic expression of human inner experiences, feelings and spiritual world. Composers of this period, such as Franz Schubert, Frederic Chopin, Franz Liszt, Johannes Brahms, created works that enriched not only their era, but also the art of all mankind.

For high school students, studying Romantic music is of great importance not only for the formation of musical perception, but also for the development of their aesthetic taste, and the expansion of their emotional and intellectual outlook. However, in order to ensure the effectiveness of this process, it is necessary to use scientifically and theoretically based approaches and modern pedagogical methods.

This study is aimed at studying the scientific and theoretical foundations of the formation of musical perception in students in the process of studying the work of romantic composers. The relevance of the study is determined by the possibilities of forming students' musical thinking and culture through the emotional and figurative features of the music of the Romantic period.

The main goal of the study is to develop and implement effective methods for the formation of musical perception for high school students based on the study of the work of romantic composers. To achieve this goal, the study

considers the characteristics of romantic music, the methodology for developing musical perception, and pedagogical approaches in the educational process.

Relevance of the topic

Today, in the educational process, special attention is paid not only to the acquisition of knowledge by students, but also to the development of aesthetic taste and cultural views. Musical art, especially the music of the romantic period, is an important tool for positively influencing the human psyche, educating emotions, and developing creative thinking. The works of romantic composers increase students' ability to listen, understand, and analyze music, and help them form a deep musical perception.

However, it is observed that insufficient attention is paid to the study of the music of the romantic period in the modern education system. There is a need for modern pedagogical methods and scientifically-theoretically based approaches to deeply explain this topic to students and develop musical perception. It is precisely because romantic music embodies emotional richness and imagery that it is one of the most effective sources for the aesthetic education of students and the formation of their creative abilities.

Therefore, the study of the issues of forming students' musical perception on a scientific and theoretical basis in the process of studying the work of romantic composers, their integration into the modern educational process, and increasing the effectiveness of musical education determine the relevance of the topic. This not only improves the quality of education, but also serves to educate people with aesthetic taste and spiritually mature individuals in society.

Conclusion:

The formation of musical perception in high school students in the process of studying the work of romantic composers is of great importance not only in educational terms, but also in educational terms. The results of this study show that the music of the romantic period is an effective tool for the aesthetic and emotional development of students and the enrichment of their musical thinking.

Features of romantic music such as imagery, deep expression of emotions and artistic complexity create a wide range of opportunities for the development of students' musical perception. The pedagogical approaches and methods identified during the study confirmed the possibility of forming a culture of listening and understanding music in students, developing their creative abilities.

It was also found that the use of interactive methods, audiovisual tools and creative exercises in the modern educational process plays an important role in the effective teaching of the work of romantic composers and the formation of musical perception.

At the end of the study, the following recommendations were developed for the development of musical perception in students:

1. Integrate the work of romantic composers into the curriculum and teach them systematically.
2. Allocate special time for listening and analysis exercises, organize discussions of students' opinions.
3. Support students' creative activities related to music.

The results of this study will serve to further enrich and increase the effectiveness of secondary school music education. At the same time, it plays an important role in the formation of students as spiritually mature individuals.

References:

1. Abdullayev A. A. Theoretical foundations of music education. Tashkent: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2018.
2. Karimov M. M. History of the art of music. Tashkent: Sharq Publishing House, 2020.
3. Rashidova N. N. Fundamentals of musical pedagogy. Tashkent: Science and Technology, 2019.
4. Barsova I. V. History of Romanticism and Music. Moscow: Muzykalnaya shkola, 2017.
6. Trigulova A. X. Musiqa tarixi (Chet el musiqa tarixi). Darslik. – T.: Lesson Press, 2021
7. Trigulova A. X. THE IMPORTANCE OF THE COURSE "HISTORY AND THEORY OF MUSIC SCIENCE" IN THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF MASTERS OF MUSICAL CULTURE FACULTIES OF PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITIES. The Bioscan, (Special Issue-1), Retrieved from 19(2): S.I (1), 2024., 191-194 6
8. Trigulova A. X. The Significance of B.Asafyev's Intonation Theory in the Instrumental-Performance Training of a Music Teacher., 192 – 195 6
9. Trigulova A. X. Musiqadagi romantizm. Monografiya. – T.: “Bookmany print” nashriyoti, 2023

